

Organizational Politics and Managerial Conflicts as Correlate of Academic Staff Productivity in Lagos State Universities, Lagos, Nigeria

Adeola Adawi Adeleke¹

adawi.adeleke@lasu.edu.ng

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6675-3046>

Nurudeen Olalekan Orunbon¹

orunbon.nurudeeno@gmail.com

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7479-2624>

&

Omobolanle Adeola Olubowale²

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0259-8623>

¹Department of Educational Management, Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria

²Alaso Community Junior High School, Alagbado, Lagos, Nigeria

Abstract

This research examined the relationship between academic staff productivity at Lagos State Universities and organisational politics and managerial conflicts. The study's objective was to ascertain how managerial conflicts and organisational politics affected the academic staff's output at Lagos State Universities in Lagos, Nigeria, from among the three Lagos State Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. Three hypotheses (tested at 0.05 level of significance) were set to serve as guides for the study. The proportionate stratified random sampling approach was used to determine the study's sample size. 30% of all lecturers at each of the three institutions that were chosen were chosen at random, according to the sampling strategy. The research included 1118 academic staff members in all. A structured questionnaire titled the Academic Staff Politics and Conflicts Questionnaire (ASPCQ) was created to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was used to collect data after ensuring their validity. The Cronbach Alphas of the instruments were determined by calculating the test-retest reliability coefficient using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The results for the Organisational Politics Scale, Staff Conflict Management Inventory, Staff Favouritism Scale, and Conflict Management Inventory were, respectively, .786, .891, .815 and .765. The findings were deemed significant at the 0.05 probability level after the data was examined using inferential statistics, namely Pearson's Product Moment Correlation for hypotheses one and two and Regression Analysis for hypothesis three. The results showed that organisational politics and academic staff productivity at Lagos State Universities were significantly correlated ($r = 0.779$, $p < 0.05$), that perceived favouritism and academic staff productivity were positively correlated ($r = 0.805$, $p < 0.05$), and that there was a significant relationship between managerial conflicts and academic staff productivity at Lagos State Universities ($r = 0.826$, $p < 0.05$). Based on the findings, the study recommends that managers in the university system should learn how to delegate power to lower-level members of staff, and training or seminars on dispute resolution procedures should be held for lecturers.

Keywords: Organisational Politics, Managerial conflict, Staff productivity, Lagos state universities.

Introduction

Organisational politics and managerial conflicts are two critical factors that can significantly impact the productivity of university lecturers. While the academic environment is often perceived as a bastion of intellectual pursuit and collaboration, underlying political dynamics and conflicts can create barriers that hinder productivity. Organisational politics refers to the activities and behaviors that individuals engage in to gain power and influence within an institution. In a university setting, this can manifest in various ways, including favoritism in promotions, resource allocation, and decision-making processes. For university lecturers, organisational politics can create a toxic work environment. When promotions are awarded based on political connections rather than merit, it can demotivate faculty members. This sense of inequity may lead to disengagement from their teaching and research responsibilities, ultimately affecting their productivity. Moreover, when lecturers perceive that their contributions are undervalued due to political dynamics, they may withdraw from collaborative projects, affecting both their professional relationships and the overall academic output of the institution. Managerial conflicts arise from disagreements over policies, resource allocation, and strategic direction within an organisation. In universities, these conflicts can occur between different administrative levels, such as between department heads and university administration or among faculty

members themselves. While organisational politics and managerial conflicts often have detrimental effects on productivity, it is essential to consider that not all political behavior is negative. In some cases, political maneuvering can lead to positive outcomes, such as the mobilization of resources for innovative projects. Similarly, conflicts can sometimes stimulate necessary discussions that lead to improved policies and practices.

An organisation is a place where individuals with different interests, experiences, and educational levels join together for work toward a common goal. An organisation is just a structure where individuals cooperate and strive toward a common goal. The level of effort put forth by each employee has a direct impact on the success of an organisation (Cacciattolo, 2013). Power and politics have a big impact on how employees interact with one another and how choices are made in organisations. How people use their power, whether it be positive or bad, to shape others at work determines the impact of power in both big and small organisations (Al-Jenaibi, 2014). Power relationships and the extent to which not a workplace's overall culture fosters productivity may be directly impacted by politics. Since politics is the essence of life, it is a natural phenomenon in all organisations. As a result, an organisation's growth depends on its capacity to manage it successfully and efficiently. Above all things, a person should put their organisation first. Commitment to one's work and a strong sense of community are essential. In order to provide their utmost effort, the employees need to work closely together. According to Shamaila (2012), organisational politics is an activity enabling people to achieve their objectives outside of the bounds of the law. This activity may be helpful, contingent upon whether the individual's goals coincide with the organisation's. However, organisational politics often reveals unethical behaviour by employees motivated just by self-interest. In pursuing their own personal preferences, even at the detriment of other employees, they could also disregard the company's goals.

There is a significant decreitive, quirky, and individualistic element in organisational politics. Therefore, different individuals may consider the same behaviour as political or non-political, depending on their history and point of view. Furthermore, politics is said to often obstruct normal organisational processes and reduce productivity and performance for both the organisation and its members. If the highly skilled employee believes that organisational politics have denied him a legitimate opportunity, he may react badly by exhibiting low satisfaction, stress, unpleasant behaviour (such as theft), and turnover. According to Odiagbe (2011), academic institution officials have spent a significant amount of their life engaged in very contentious political battles instead of concentrating their efforts on productive teaching, learning, and research. Organisational politics in higher education often aim to safeguard or promote individual interests or, on the other hand, to prevent negative outcomes from happening inside the organisation (Ferris & Kacmar, 2011). The use of one's institutional or personal authority to seek advantages that beyond one's legitimacy is referred to as organisational politics in the realm of higher education. These advantages might take the shape of physical access to assets or intangible advantages like status or a fictitious perception of power that influences the behaviour of others. Individuals inside a corporation have personal and role-specific preferences when it comes to organisational behaviour and laws. However, when employees are unable to do the desired action, conflict arises or occurs. Because of this, the university's administration and employees sometimes clash, which may eventually result in strikes and reduce and disrupt employee productivity (Akpooyovwaire, 2013).

Therefore, organisational politics and conflict may lead to ineffective interpersonal interaction, diminished output, discontent, lack of dedication, and low productivity. Therefore, the goal of this study is to find out how organisational politics and management conflicts impact academic staff members' production in state-controlled institutions in Lagos. The continual exercise of office power is causing discontent, disagreement, and lower productivity among university administrators and academic personnel. Staff grievances, such as termination for prejudice, the application of leadership to impede staff performance, declines to renew contracts, etc., have been raised in the university system recently. These issues are sometimes prompted by politics at work, and interpersonal communication and miscommunication among academic staff often escalate and lead to management disputes between academic staff and university administrators. Due to insufficient means of communication on educational institution rules, changes in working procedures, and the implementation of new policies that affect their lives, academic staff members encounter conflicts, feelings of dread, confusion, and rage. The efficient, effective, and smooth running of institutions has been impeded by the distrust and hostility that have resulted from these problems between professionals and academics. Additionally, it seems that many people working in education are oddly unconcerned about this danger despite the situation. Conflict may have a negative effect on management and staff if it is not addressed because people involved often exhibit a reluctance to do their jobs, which reduces university faculty productivity. This problem may be caused by individuals who misuse organisational politics to manipulate their working relationships and squander time and resources for their own gain at the expense of the team or organisation.

The following hypotheses stated in null form were tested in this study:

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between organisational politics and productivity of academic staff in Lagos State universities.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived favouritism and productivity of academic staff in Lagos State universities.

Ho₃: There is no relative contributions of perceived organisational politics and managerial conflict on the productivity of academic staff in Lagos State universities.

"Productivity" refers to the economical and effective use of everything that is available, including materials, labour, money, time, energy, and knowledge. Productivity is the process by which an economy or business uses resources like labour and capital to create outputs, or goods and services. Adedayo (2017) states that it may be defined as the output to input ratio. The ratio of output to input needed for manufacturing is known as productivity. According to Broman in Nwamadi and Ogbonna (2021), increasing staff productivity is one of the organisation's primary objectives. An employee's knowledge, abilities, motivation, and behaviours all affect productivity. It is defined as the amount or degree of output (sales, profits, and market share) that comes from a certain input (production expenditures, labour hours, or material/equipment charges).

Productivity, as defined by the U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics, is a metric used to assess economic performance that contrasts the quantity of products and services produced (output) with the quantity of inputs required to generate them. Productivity denotes the extent to which a given set of inputs may be efficiently used to generate an output. Productivity is often calculated by dividing output by input. A higher ratio indicates more productivity. On the other hand, a drop in the ratio of output to input signifies a decrease in productive time (Pooja & Sachin, 2015). In Adedapo & Ajayi (2021), Kaniki defines the effectiveness with which lecturers fulfill their various responsibilities, including knowledge and scholarship (the result of research and other scholarly activities), learning (the result of imparting knowledge), and organisational, community, and professional well-being (the results of professional activities, community service, and cooperative leadership). Maintaining the productivity of academic staff seems to be essential for survival in the fiercely competitive higher education market of today.

The rate at which faculty members accomplish their own goals in proportion to the institution's goals is known as academic staff productivity. The degree of production varies with teachers. These discrepancies may not be related to the university's usage of social security, health care, and promotion initiatives, as well as performance evaluations (Abdulkareem, 2015). To advance to higher levels of the service, professors must also complete courses that lead to higher education degrees, publish in credible journals, textbooks, articles, and papers, and do community service. Therefore, both the productivity of the lecturers and the general efficiency of the institutions are increased when their skills are strengthened via various programs such as seminars, workshops, mentoring, further education, introductory courses, and the establishment of suitable reference libraries. According to Adeyemi (2010), academic productivity can be measured in a number of ways, such as teaching, lesson planning, subject matter expertise, dedication to extracurricular and academic pursuits, efficient student work supervision, classroom management, disciplinary skills, and personal growth.

Organisational politics, or prioritizing one's own desires beyond those of the organisation, is a crucial component of every organisation's operation. Ferris and Kacmar (2011) provided a precise definition of organisational politics using the phrase "the degree to which worker consider their work environment as governmental in character that serves to make individuals consider their environment unfair and unjust." Nowadays, this term is widely used. An employee's attitude and character are influenced by the political climate, and employee behaviour in an organisation is often seen as political. Politics, according to Aristotle (1934), is a "master-craft" and a desirable social phenomenon (Provis in Vigoda-Gadot & Drory, 2006). However, the general definition of organisational politics is to protect the self-interest of one individual at the expense of another (Drory & Vigoda-Gadot, 2010; Ferris 1989; Gotsisamd Kortezi, 2010; Latif, 2011; Vigoda-Gadot and Kapun, 2005; Cacciattolo, 2013). This mindset often conflicts with the company's objectives (Ladebo, 2006, Sussman, 2002; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007). According to Vigoda-Gadot and Drory (2006), contend that organisational politics is a "antisocial" behaviour. According to Vredenburg and Shea Van-Fossen (2010), there is a hypothesis that suggests the obvious political tendencies of human nature are the result of evolution. This tendency is linked to the desire for power and arises from the interplay between rank delineation and employment allocation. Vigoda-Gador and Drory, (2006) argue that certain people would not be motivated to participate in politics if they had nothing to gain from using political strategies. Those who gain from political behaviour may feel content or even delighted, according to Liu (2006), quoted in Vigoda-Gadot and Drory (2006), particularly if obtaining favorable outcomes calls for the use of dubious tactics.

It is also possible to see organisational politics as a phenomenon that only occurs inside certain organisations, where members may not actively participate in politics. People often create informal groupings and alliances with one another at work (Seo, 2003). Organisational cultural values have the power to strengthen or weaken group politics and may influence the direction of group politics (James, in Vigoda-Gadot & Drory, 2006). These might be any of the many different types of groupings, such as managers and subordinates in a department, employees at the same level of the hierarchy, or colleagues in a same social circle. Other interested groups in an organisation that could take political action include unions and employers

(Romm & Pliskin, 1997). The most recent perspective is interactionism, which argues that disagreement is essential to a group's ability to function and even implies that internal conflict may be beneficial (Robbins & Sanghi, 2008).

Methodology

Descriptive survey research was the method used for this investigation. Because it methodically examines phenomena, particularly the characteristics of a particular population or region of interest, this design is perfect for application in this research. Additionally, describing the variables in question as they already exist is the goal of descriptive survey study design. Instead of changing any of the factors, the researcher provided an unbiased account of the phenomena as they are. All of the faculty members at the three tertiary institutions operated by Lagos State made up the study's population. Below is a breakdown of the population:

Table 1: Study Population

S/N	Tertiary Institutions	No. of Employees
1	Lagos State University, Ojo	1982
2	Lagos State University of Education, Ijanikin	878
3	Lagos State University of Technology, Ikorodu	865
Total		3725

Source: Personnel Departments of the Respective Tertiary Institution (2024).

The proportionate stratified random sampling approach was used to determine the study's sample size. 30% of all lecturers at each of the three institutions that were chosen were to be chosen at random, according to the sampling strategy. 595 faculty members from Lagos State University, 263 faculty members from Lagos State University of Education, and 260 faculty members from Lagos State University of Technology make up the sample. There were 1,118 responders in all.

For this investigation, a trustworthy tool was used. A self-created survey called 'Academic Staff Politics and Conflicts Questionnaire (ASPCQ)' which comprised of four scales namely;

1. Organisational Politics Scale (OPS)
2. Staff Conflict Management Inventory (SCMI)
3. Staff Favouritism scale (SFS)
4. Staff Productivity Scale (SPS)

The ASPCQ was divided into four sections (A, B, C and D sections). Section A will be on the respondent's bio-data which gathered information on respondent's background such as: 'Gender', 'age', 'staff category', 'years of service and experience', While sections B, C, D and E was on Perceived Organisational Politics Scale, Staff Conflict Management Inventory, Staff Favouritism Scale and Staff Productivity Scale. To assess the reliability of the items in the instrument that was utilized in this research, a pilot test was conducted. The test-retest approach was used to assess the instrument's reliability. Fifty instructors from the University of Lagos were given the instrument. Two weeks later, the same survey was given to the same instructors once again. The Cronbach Alphas of the instruments were then determined by calculating the test-retest reliability coefficient using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The results for the Organisational Politics Scale, Staff Conflict Management Inventory, Staff Favouritism Scale, and Conflict Management Inventory were, respectively, .786, .891, .815 and .765.

The researcher distributed the instrument by hand during a face-to-face conversation. This was done in order to guarantee that every questionnaire was returned in full and to get an honest answer from the respondent. At the 0.05 level of significance, the completed Academic Staff Politics and Conflicts Questionnaire items were gathered, categorized, and subjected to inferential statistics using regression analysis for hypothesis three, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation for hypotheses 1 and 2.

Results

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant correlation between Organisational politics and productivity of academic staff in Lagos State owned universities.

Table 2:
Result of Correlation between Organisational Politics and Productivity of Academic Staff in Lagos State Universities

		Organisational Politics	Staff Productivity
Organisational Politics	Pearson Correlation	1	.779**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	1118	1118
Staff Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.779**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	1118	1118

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to the test's results, academic staff productivity at Lagos State-owned institutions is positively correlated with organisational politics ($r = 0.778$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis, according to which organisational politics and academic staff productivity at institutions controlled by the State of Lagos do not significantly correlate, is now rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between perceived favouritism and productivity of academic staff in Lagos State owned universities.

Table 3: Result of Relationship between Perceived Favouritism and Productivity of Academic Staff in Lagos State owned universities.

		Perceived Favouritism	Academic Staff Productivity
Perceived Favouritism	Pearson Correlation	1	.895**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	1118	1118
Academic Staff Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.895**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	1118	1118

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The test's result shows that there is a positive significant relationship between academic staff productivity in Lagos State-owned universities and perceived favouritism ($r = 0.895$, $p < 0.05$). Accordingly, the null hypothesis, which holds that there is no significant relationship between academic staff productivity and perceived favouritism in Lagos State-owned universities, is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There is no relative contributions of perceived organisational politics and managerial conflict on the productivity of academic staff in Lagos State Universities.

Table 4:
Regression Result of Relative Contributions of Perceived Organisational Politics and Managerial Conflict on the Productivity of Academic Staff in Lagos State Universities

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	3.786	.446		8.496	.000
	Organisational Politics	.277	.019	.352	14.726	.000
	Managerial Conflict	.588	.025	.558	23.316	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Staff Productivity

The statistical model description of the relative effects of management conflict and perceived organisational politics on academic staff productivity at institutions controlled by the State of Lagos is shown in Table 4. The findings indicate that academic staff productivity at Lagos State-owned institutions is positively and significantly correlated with perceived organisational politics and management conflict. 0.857 is the correlation coefficient (R). The outcome further suggests that perceptions of management disputes and organisational politics vary. $R^2 = 0.735$ indicates that organisational politics and management conflicts account for 73.5% of the changes in academic staff productivity, whereas other variables not included in this research account for 26.5% of the variations.

It was also noted that organisational politics ($\beta = .277$, $t = 14.726$, $p < 0.05$) came before management disputes, which contributed the most to academic staff productivity at Lagos State-owned institutions ($\beta = .588$, $t = 23.316$, $p < 0.05$). Given that the independent variables' p values are below the 0.05 threshold of significance, it is possible to draw the conclusion from the data that each independent variable's contribution is statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis—which holds that perceived organisational politics and management conflict have no appreciable relative effects on academic staff productivity at institutions controlled by the Lagos State is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

According to the study's initial goal, which was to investigate the link between academic staff productivity and organisational politics, the results showed that the two variables do, in fact, have a positive association, supporting the hypothesis. This suggests that the productivity of academic personnel at work is significantly impacted by organisational politics. This current conclusion is in line with that of Abbas and Awan (2017), who found that organisational politics significantly affect worker performance. Their study's conclusions reaffirmed the necessity for management to comprehend how staff members see the organisational politics that are in place in their companies and to implement measures that would reduce employee perceptions of these politics while improving worker performance. In their research, Opoku and Arthur (2018) also discovered a favorable and substantial correlation between Ghanaian public sector employees' dedication and their opinions of organisational politics. Senior employees perceive greater organisational politics than younger employees, according to Adebusuyi, Olasupo, and Idehen (2013).

According to the second hypothesis, which was supported by the calculation and analysis of the study's data, there is a substantial correlation between academic staff productivity in Lagos State-owned institutions and perceived favouritism. This suggests that academic staff members' degree of bias may impair their level of efficiency at work. This is corroborated by the research of Arubayi and Eruvbedede (2022), who found that partiality has a statistically significant impact on employee performance. Furthermore, a research by Ombanda (2018) shown that nepotism has a detrimental impact on workers' job performance. Ombanda's research also showed that nepotism does not penalize bad performance and that an employee's qualifications or competence are irrelevant when nepotism is implemented. Favouritism is often used by top management, which may be the cause of the notable effects it has on worker productivity. It also probably influences how workers behave and commit to their jobs inside the organisation.

According to the third hypothesis, academic staff productivity at institutions owned by the State of Lagos is positively and significantly correlated with organisational politics and management disputes. The factors of management disputes and organisational politics account for 73.5% of the productivity of university academic personnel. This research suggests that disagreement might affect academic staff productivity in both good and bad ways. Ineffective conflict resolution may have a negative impact on the organisation's performance, degree of collaboration, resource waste, and productivity. Additionally, it enhances the organisation's capacity for innovation and makes better choices when it comes to dispute resolution. Therefore, these data imply that management conflicts and organisational politics are significant variables that independently contribute to the explanation of academic staff productivity.

Conclusion

The study showed how perceived organisational politics and managerial disputes relate to the productivity of academic personnel at institutions controlled by the State of Lagos. The statistical results of the research corroborate the notion that perceived organisational politics and academic staff productivity are favorably connected. Furthermore, it may be argued that the positive relationship between management conflicts and productivity has a major impact on the productivity of academic staff in State of Lagos-controlled schools. Moreover, it may be deduced that 73.5% of academic staff members' potential production is accounted for by organisational politics and managerial conflicts. The study also shown that different genders respond differently to organisational politics and perceived managerial conflict. In particular, males thought their employment was more political than women's. Academic staff members may react to university politics more destructively and actively and

consider sacrificing tenure and job security if they perceive organisational politics to be widespread. This is riskier since it might indicate dissatisfaction with the organisation's culture and jeopardize academic staff members' career progress and occupational status. Creating a political-free work environment for workers may increase productivity.

Recommendations

The following suggestions were made in light of the results in order to improve the productivity of academic staff in universities controlled by Lagos State.

1. The management of Lagos State colleges should put a lot of effort into controlling political behaviour as it would improve workers' effectiveness on the job.
2. By identifying the underlying cause and eliminating it permanently, university administrators should implement efficient conflict avoidance and resolution procedures in Lagos State institutions.
3. Organisations should provide training sessions for their employees on dispute resolution techniques.
4. In order to prevent needless management disputes and ongoing industrial strikes, which often impair academic staff productivity, the government should also investigate the wellbeing of its employees.

References

- Abbas, Q., & Awan, S. H. (2017). Impact of organisational politics on employee performance in public sector organisations. *Pakistan Administrative Review*, 1(1), 19-31. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-51861-8>
- Abdulkareem, R. L. (2015). Lecturers Job Commitment, Corporate Culture and University Goal Achievement in the Southwest Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria. A PhD. Thesis Submitted to the Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Adebusuyi, A.S; Olasupo, M. O & Idehen, E.E (2013). Analysis of the Perception of Organisational Politics by Employees of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Bangladeshe Journal of Sociology*, 10(01), 51 - 38.
- Adedapo, A. A., & Ajayi, I. A. (2021). Human Resource Management and Academic Staff Productivity in Tertiary Institutions in Southwest, Nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 8(9), 524-530.
- Adedayo, A. E. (2017). Performance Management and Employee Productivity of Selected Manufacturing Companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Master of Business Administration Dissertation, Babcock University Alishan-Remo Ogun State Nigeria.
- Akpoyovwaire, S.M. (2013). Conflict Management and Resolution Strategies for Enhanced Personnel Productivity and Sustainable Administration in Higher Institutions in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 6(4), 365-371.
- Al-Jenaibi, B. (2014). Managing Conflict in Workplace: A case study in the UAE organisations. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Communication*, 49 - 81.
- Allen. R. W. (1979). Organisational politics - Tactics and characteristics of its actors, California. *Management Review*, 22(1), 7-83.
- Arubayi, O.D. & Eruvbedede, K.O. (2022). Effects of Workplace Harassment and Favouritism on Staff Performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)* 10(9), 3851-3860, DOI: 10.18535/ijrm/v10i9.em04.
- Cacciattolo K. (2013). To what extent do Organisational politics hinder or support workplace learning? The University of Malta Case. A Doctoral Thesis, Centre for Labour Market Studies, University of Leicester.
- Drory, A. & Vigoda-Gadot, E. (2010). Organisational politics and human resource management: A typology and the Israeli experience. *Human Resource Management Review*, 20, 194-202.
- Ferris G. R., & Kacmar, K. M. (1992). Perceptions of organisational politics. *Journal of Management*, 93-116.
- Ferris, G. R. & Kacmar, K. M. (2011). Perception of Organisational Politics. *Journal of Management*, 18(3), 93 – 116.
- Ladebo O. J. (2006). Perceptions of Organisational Politics: Examination of a Situational Antecedent and Consequences Among Nigeria's Extension Personnel. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 255-281.
- Latif A. (2011). Individual Political Behaviour in Organisational relationship. *Journal of Politics and Law*, 199-210.
- Nwamadi B. C. & Ogbonna, O.P (2021). A Survey of Academic Staff Productivity in Selected Universities in Southwest, Nigeria. *Helsinki Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 84-95.
- Odiagbe, S. A. (2011). Industrial conflict in Nigerian universities: A Case Study of the Disputes Between the Academic Staff Union of Universities and the Federal Government of Nigeria. A Research Thesis, School of Social and Political Sciences, College of Social Sciences, University of Glasgow.
- PoojaYadav, & Col. SachinMarwah (2015). The Concept of Productivity. *International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research (IJETR)* 3(5), 192-196.
- Robbins & Sanghi (2008). *Organisational Behaviour* (12th Ed.)
- Romm C.T. & Pliskin N. (1997). Toward a Virtual Politicking Model. *Communications of the ACM*, 95-100.
- Samaila M, Uzochukwu, O.C., & Ishaq, M (2018). Organisational Politics and Workplace Conflict in Selected Tertiary Institutions in Edo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Social Sciences*. 4(1), 26-41, DOI: 10.20448/2001.41.26.41
- Seo M. G. (2003). Overcoming Emotional Barriers, Political Obstacles, and Control Imperative in the Action-Science Approach to Individual and Organisational Learning. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 7-21.
- Sussman L. (2002). Organisational politics: Tactics, Channels, and Hierarchical Roles. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 313-329.
- Vigoda-Gadot E. (2007). Leadership style, Organisational Politics and Employees' Performance; An Empirical Examination of two Competing Models. *Personnel Review*, 661-683.
- Vigoda-Gadot E. & Drory A. (Eds) (2006). *Handbook of Organisational Politics*.
- Vigoda-Gadot E. & Kapun D. (2005). Perceptions of Politics and Perceived Performance in Public and Private Organisations: A Test on one Model across two Sections. *Policy & Politics*, 251-276.
- Vredenburg D. & Shea Van- Fossen R. (2010). Human nature, Organisational Politics and Human Resource Development Review.